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Gender equality and research

Jabbarova Sevara Shukhratovna

Student of the Department of Political Science of the Uzbek University of
Journalism and Mass Communications

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ayolla va erkaklarning jamiyatdagi huquqlari, qolaversa, bugungi kunda ayollar duch kelayotgan muammolar keltirilgan.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются права женщин и мужчин в обществе, а также проблемы, с которыми сегодня сталкиваются женщины.

Annotation: This article examines the rights of women and men in society, as well as the problems that women face today.

Kalit so'zlar: Gender tengligi, tadqiqotlar, zo'rvonlik, Skandinaviya mamlakatlari, sabab va yechimlar, ustunlik.

Ключевые слова: Гендерное равенство, исследования, насилие, скандинавские страны, причины и решения, превосходство.

Keywords: Gender equality, research, violence, Scandinavian countries, causes and solutions, superiority.

Women and girls make up half of the world's population, which is equivalent to half of humanity's potential. Gender equality, one of the most important human rights, plays a key role in ensuring peace and harmony in society and the full realization of human potential on the basis of sustainable development. It is proved that the involvement of women in the life of society ensures the growth of productivity and economic growth.

The issue of gender equality is one of the Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the UN. The question arises: why is so much attention paid to this issue? And all because there are a lot of cases of violence against women in the world.

You have noticed that in primary school, both girls and boys master at the same level, for example, mathematics, chemistry, physics, but after moving to high school, boys begin to learn better. **American Professor Robert Sapolsky** conducts research on this issue and presented it as a fact in his book "**Behave The biology of humans at our best and worths**". An example of this is the fact that in the USA in 1983, for a girl who scored 1 high on the sat exam, there were 11 children who scored higher. A total

of 8 percent said that only girls received higher scores, the main reason for this was that it was believed that men were more active and therefore different because of the hormone testosterone, which, of course, attracts attention. These facts are given by a man.

But in 2008, an extensive study was conducted by **Professor Paulo Sapienza of The presidents Circle of Northwestern University in the USA**, which showed that the difference in the activity of girls and boys is caused by innate biological reasons or social reasons. And, according to this, it is social instability that determines why girls show poor results not only in mathematics, but also in other fields. But in the Scandinavian countries, the opposite is observed, that is, girls and boys in these developed countries have established gender equality, their rights in society are the same. For example, if you are trying to get a job at Gashkilot, they are looking at vacancies designed for 10 women and 10 men. According to this study, it is in **Turkey that the lowest level of proficiency in mathematics is observed-23%**.

At the moment, **750 million girls** around the world have married under the **age of 18**. You can say that they are chubby, but they have not yet matured as individuals, they go to a new family, they run a household, and, as a rule, it is easy to manage them, as well as hinder their growth. It is reported that in **18 states**, husbands can legally not allow their wives to work. Pretending to kick the dead, **in 39 states**, the rights of women and men are not equal in the matter of inheritance.

So, as things stand in Uzbekistan, although the Muslim population in Uzbekistan is the majority, violence is observed daily. When the people we know as men abuse women, beat, humiliate, humiliate and demonstrate their strength to a woman, should we call her a man again? And all this is rooted somewhere in the family and even in women who are used to it and believe that it should be so. The lack of equality in the family is manifested in the fact that mothers themselves force their son to do everything possible, forbidding the girl everything. In fact, the girls were emotional or empty, maybe that's how they are brought up.

The problem of gender equality, the creation of equal opportunities for women on an equal footing with men has been on the agenda of international life for more than a decade. The principle of gender equality is declared in fundamental international human rights instruments, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and many other international conventions. Nevertheless, even in the third decade of the XXI century, this problem has not been completely solved. Thus, for a quarter of a century,

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none of the countries of the world has achieved the full realization of the goals of the Beijing Declaration on the Rights of Women of 1995. Three quarters of all managers in the world are still men and only one quarter are women.

In 2023, the leaders in the overall level of gender equality were:

Iceland;

Norway;

Finland;

New Zealand;

Sweden;

Germany;

Nicaragua;

Namibia;

Lithuania;

Belgium.

At the end of the ranking are Pakistan, Iran, Algeria, Chad and Afghanistan.

Eight basic indicators were calculated: wages, employment, running your own business, managing assets owned by women, pension provision, freedom of movement, as well as marriage and having children.

Russia scored 73.13 out of 100 points on this indicator, lagging behind most of the former USSR countries, except Uzbekistan. That is, these data already show us the situation in Uzbekistan.

In Uzbekistan, being a female representative is not an easy matter. Often, almost every day they have to face trouble from guys, men. It's elementary to look at women with a wild "hungry" look, call them names, etc. These are just banal, absurd examples.

In addition, not to allow women to work, claiming to them that a woman's place is exclusively at home, thus infringing on their rights, not to let them speak out and express their opinion, make any decisions on their own, and a bunch of similar examples: this is a real trouble!

However, today we still see problems of gender equality arising in almost all spheres of our life:

The difference in wages. An interesting fact is that in the USA women are more educated than men. Among them there are more bachelor's, master's and doctorate degrees. The question arises, why do women in the U.S. workforce still earn less than

their male counterparts? According to the Institute for Women's Political Studies, women earn 49 cents against every \$1 earned by men. In the world, the gender pay gap is 23%, and in rural areas it reaches a whopping 40%.

Sexual harassment. This is the main problem that women face in the workplace. A survey conducted in January 2018 by the non-profit organization Stop Street Harassment showed that 38% of women had been sexually harassed in the workplace, and 81% reported having experienced some form of sexual harassment during their lifetime, including verbal or physical attacks. In addition, restaurant workers and persons who do not have legal immigration status or have a temporary work visa are 2 times more likely to be sexually harassed.

Racism. The salary a woman receives may vary depending on her race and ethnicity. Data from the Institute for Women's Policy Research showed that women from the Asia-Pacific region have the highest average annual earnings and receive compensation in the amount of US\$46,000. White women receive \$40,000, while Native American (Indian) and Hispanic women receive the lowest salaries — \$31,000 and \$28,000 per year.

It is more difficult for women to break through the career ladder than for men. Despite the high level of education among the female half of the population, only 5% of CEOs and 10% of women with the best earnings in the S&P 500 stock index are among them. With other races, things are even worse, they are practically not found in the S&P 500 or Fortune 500 rankings. One of the reasons why a woman does not move to senior positions is the lack of female role models in the workplace. Catalyst.org he says that the lack of a visible role model can make a girl feel that the transition to the role of leader is simply unattainable.

Domestic violence in the family. This problem is much more global than it seems. In 49 countries of the world, there is still no legislative framework that would criminalize domestic violence. Only 30% of women in the world who are in a relationship report physical or sexual violence by a partner. According to WHO research, 35% of the female population has been subjected to violence by an intimate partner or a third person at least once in their life. Here it is impossible not to note the frightening criminal picture — 38% of murders are committed by male partners.

Fears related to the request for a salary increase. The discussion of wages is often associated with greed or despair among the female half. A new Glassdoor study

has found that women negotiate their salaries less often than their male counterparts. The survey showed that almost 70% of women accepted the proposed salary without discussion, while 52% of men did the same.

Despite the achievements in the field of gender equality, young girls and adult women everywhere in the world suffer from violence and discrimination. To ensure gender equality of men and women, it is necessary to actively carry out the following tasks:

- To combat all forms of violence against the female half of the population, including human trafficking and sexual exploitation.
- Eliminate discrimination against girls and women in all spheres of life.
- Abolish forced and early marriages.
- Eliminate operations that cripple female genitalia. This practice is common in Africa and the Middle East.
- To enable women to really participate in political, social and economic decision-making.
- Encourage unpaid work (here we mean housekeeping) through social protection.
- Provide women with equal rights to economic and natural resources, ownership of land and other real estate, inheritance and financial services.

If in developed countries ensuring gender equality is one of the main tasks, then in many developing countries this issue is still open.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. <https://mentamore.com/socium/gendernoe-ravenstvo>
2. <https://myfin.by/stati/view/opublikovan-rejting-stran-po-urovnu-gendernogo-ravenstva>
3. Силласте Г. Г. Социальные транзисии и формирование нового гендерного порядка // Женщина в российском обществе. 2019.
4. Коннелл Р. Гендер и власть. Общество, личность и гендерная политика/пер. с англ. Т. Барчунова. – М.: Новое литературное обозрение, 2015

